

THOTH OPEN METADATA COPIM OPEN BOOK FUTURES MIDTERM REVIEW

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INTRODUCTION

The Open Book Futures project (OBF) launched in May 2023, and is set to run until April 2026. It is a follow-up project to the earlier Copim project (2019-2023). One of the aims of OBF is to enable Thoth Open Metadata to become an integral component of the Open Access (OA) book publishing ecosystem. Thoth is directly involved in three of the seven OBF work packages.

Thoth is dedicated to advancing OA publishing and supporting the scholarly community. It provides innovative metadata management and distribution solutions tailored to tackle the problems of getting OA works into the book supply chain, ensuring their long-term sustainability and accessibility.

Thoth's main goals are:

- To lower the entry barrier to good metadata management practices for small/medium OA publishers who are currently struggling to produce their metadata to the different specifications that each distributing platform requires.
- To help distribute OA books, which have been systematically excluded from a book supply chain that was created for closed books.
- To expose quality and first-hand metadata, using industry standards, publicly for anyone to consume.

Thoth Open Metadata's key stakeholders are:

- The community of small- to medium-sized academic publishers active in publishing OA books.
- Libraries that provide access to academic books.

Indirect stakeholders are the authors of scholarly books, as well as readers, and the general public, who benefit from free, immediate access to knowledge.

This independent report will review the company's efforts to deliver on these goals, its business model, catalogue of services and how Thoth is perceived by its key stakeholders. Moreover, it focuses on the Thoth Strategic Roadmap for the coming five years. Input for this review were three 3-hour workshops with the Thoth team (attended by ca. 8 pp each workshop), interviews with stakeholders and desk research.

CONTEXT & LANDSCAPE

Open science and open book publishing are rooted in an ever changing social, economic and political context. The last 20 years, open science has been able to grow by funding and law, particularly in the global North. Fundamental choices have been made to support open science to enable *more open and collaborative research practices in which publications, data, software and other types of academic output are shared at the earliest possible stage and made available for reuse*¹. This year we see a change in political climate leading to crunching budgets and even websites going dark² so this is more relevant than ever.

University libraries are reconsidering the current 'triple pay model' and therefore are motivated to support the infrastructure that enables OA publications as an alternative for traditional publishing. However, the overall change is slow, and the landscape for book publishing is even more complex than that of journal articles:

1. It is populated by a variety of different actors; commercial publishers, established university presses, library initiatives, smaller non-profits, including independent scholar-led publishers, software platforms for self publishing, and a variety of for-profit, commercial, as well as non-profit infrastructures - all contributing to the wider OA books ecosystem.
2. No single OA model has yet positioned itself as dominant. The mix of traditional book publishers and innovation has resulted in a whole range of business models: recover publishing costs from the author, sometimes funded via projects, supported by universities so no cost to authors and readers.

Moreover, there is a lack of means for OA publishing in the global south and therefore a lack of funding and budget to pay for OA Books services, which is needed to increase bibliodiversity and the quality and pluriformity of research. This can be compensated by a model of solidarity in which the Western publishers pay a higher fee in order to be able to grant access to services for publishers in the global south. Thoth is offering this model of solidarity, but this is not a common strategy in the larger publishing ecosystem.

¹ www.nwo.nl/en/open-science

² www.nbcnews.com/politics/politics-news/federal-websites-temporarily-go-dark-order-comply-trump-dei-directive-rcna190244

WHERE DO WE STAND?

Before using Thoth, OA publishers often encountered limitations with traditional tools like spreadsheets, including difficulty in generating various output formats, manual data entry prone to errors, and time-consuming distribution processes. OA books were not disseminated widely, and the reach of smaller publishers was minimised, also because commercial services are not affordable or non-existent.

Thoth streamlines their processes, making metadata management more efficient and error-free. Looking at the OBF Project Plan, Thoth is well underway to deliver on its aims within the scope of the project.

ACCOMPLISHMENTS: CREDIBILITY

In line with the core values of the Copim community and the OBF project, Thoth is a values-driven company across all its different aspects.

Thoth stands for:

- A community owned alternative to traditional services
- User friendly, simple workflows you can trust, from experts who understand the problem

All Thoth's software is open source, allowing for transparency, community contributions, and continuous improvement. Publishers can freely access and leverage Thoth tools through open APIs, enabling seamless integration with platforms and publisher workflows to meet their specific needs. With bibliodiversity and equitable sustainability as two of Thoth's key tenets, engagement with publishers from a variety of regional contexts has been sought early on.

It is set up as a **non-profit**, large membership community interest company (CIC). This means the members collectively decide when and how the overall membership will grow. The Membership approves the appointments of Thoth's Board of Directors, which is responsible for proper management of the company's business.

ACCOMPLISHMENTS: SCOPE

At the moment, over **50 publishers** from a variety of regional contexts (incl. the UK, Europe, Africa, Latin America, United States) are using the Thoth system.

To establish a second source of funding, Thoth has been working with **university libraries** who recognise the social value Thoth is providing via participation in the Open Book Collective (OBC) funding package. Through this package, over 30 academic libraries internationally have committed to support Thoth.

On 1st April 2025, Thoth catalogue consisted of 2,800+ books and more than 13,000 chapters.

ACCOMPLISHMENTS: BUSINESS MODEL AND SERVICES

Thoth's ambition is to **create value** for the OA Books ecosystem by developing products and services that are tailored to the needs of publishers seeking to publish and widely disseminate their open access books and chapters. Thoth's first funding stream was from participation in the Copim project. Since Thoth's basic running costs are low, functional sustainability was achievable within the scope of this project. This provided the team with the resources to set up Thoth and develop services.

An important element of Thoth's business model is its open nature. When using Thoth, publishers retain full control over their data and operations, they are not locked into any specific platform or service, and they can integrate seamlessly with other platforms and workflows. There are no known other companies that offer this unique combination of an open business model and these metadata services.

"SciELO is a database that only indexes academic books that are peer-reviewed. Thoth tools and services complement SciELO, because they enable our users to also index books that are not indexed in SciELO. There has been a great need for this for a long time, but until now these kinds of services were very restrictive. Thoth is open, it's accessible and therefore an important new player for publishers in Latin America. There is also an interest in the paid-for Thoth Plus services, so it is much appreciated that Thoth offers pricing based on local markets".

Amanda Ramalho, SciELO Books Coordinator, SciELO Brazil

The two main services offered at the point of writing are:

Thoth Free

Publishers have free and unlimited self-service access to the Thoth metadata platform, through which they can create, manage and export metadata following diverse industry standards as well as platform-specific configurations thereof.

Thoth Plus

Publishers are provided with a set of managed services sending metadata and book files to key stakeholders in the larger book supply chain on behalf of a publisher. Corresponding workflows have now been established to register DOIs with Crossref, and to disseminate to platforms incl. Amazon, Google Books, JSTOR, Project MUSE, and OAPEN, as well as major academic metadata aggregators active in the field of scholarly publishing such as EBSCO, ProQuest, the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB), OCLC WorldCat, Web of Science, etc. Further workflows facilitate OA Books archiving. Thoth also offers additional services such as bespoke metadata creation (working from the PDF file of an OA book), and data ingest of a publisher's back catalogue into the Thoth database.

"The University of London Press does not use Thoth services for title management: we have our own title management system that we use for our metadata. For us Thoth is important as an intermediary platform for disseminating our metadata to a diverse set of OA platforms".

Jamie Bowman, Production Manager University of London Press

Portfolio developments

Thoth is in the process of further diversifying its service portfolio for small publishers by offering hosting and privacy-respecting usage statistics for OA books. Thoth has begun with the roll-out of hosting services to provide an easy means for publishers to make their content, metadata, and websites accessible via an integrated package built on open-source software. Next to that, Thoth is working to implement privacy-respecting usage statistics across multiple platforms, utilising the non-profit and open-source OPERAS Metrics framework as an equitable way to enable publishers to keep track of the variety of locations their OA works are being downloaded and read from.

At this point, Thoth is well-positioned to provide the technical capabilities to explore new pathways that will contribute to more interoperable open services together with other open infrastructures. Collaborations with like-minded stakeholders active in the field of OA book publishing are being sought e.g. via a Working Group within the OPERAS

network that will be focusing on Open Infrastructures for OA Books, which will be coordinated via Thoth.

Furthermore, Thoth is listed in major open infrastructure overviews, such as Invest in Open Infrastructures' InfraFinder, and the OPERAS Pathfinder. Thoth engages with OA books infrastructures globally, including OAPEN, Crossref, ROR, ORCID, PKP, African Platform for Open Scholarship (APOS), SciELO Books, OAeBU Data Trust and COKI/BAD. Thoth is also actively advocating for open data and usage of PIDs in OA book publishing across international communities. These include COMET, Barcelona Declaration signatories and the Knowledge Equity Network (KEN).

ACCOMPLISHMENTS: MARKETING AND STAKEHOLDER SATISFACTION

Regarding the marketing strategy of Thoth, feedback from stakeholders in the interviews conducted for this report is that it is easy to find clear information about Thoth and its services. The proposition of Thoth is well known amongst all involved in OA book publishing. There is an opportunity to expand towards medium-sized, more traditional university presses who probably would also benefit from these services and are struggling with the same things.

Thoth is seen as a values-based company that is very vocal and a spider in the web of the OA Book community. It is much appreciated that Thoth's payment schemes are adjusted to local markets, not only by the publishers from the markets that pay less; other publishers also see this as a fair way to support the global bibliodiversity from which all can benefit.

Metadata is a crucial part of the OA publishing process and publishers that are using Thoth's services highlight a central need for the services offered by Thoth. Thoth's open services are seen as unique, important elements in the OA Book ecosystem that build on existing infrastructure and connect to existing services. The response from the field to the new services has also been very positive.

Feedback from the side of libraries is that the impact of sponsoring Thoth is clear. The fact that they can support a range of OA Books initiatives in one go via the Open Book Collective is seen as crucial: to only support Thoth would take too much effort to pursuit. Therefore, this collaboration via the OBC seems effective for this revenue stream.

“These last 15 years, it has been incredibly hard to set up infrastructure for OA books. Now, it seems we have turned a corner: this kind of infrastructure is recognised as an essential component in the whole space of open science. There is now an understanding that institutions, and libraries in particular, should help sustain these kinds of infrastructure. Thoth is an important building block in this following the scaling small principle: the idea that you can do much more than you’re able to do by yourself, if you build on existing infrastructure and connect with existing services”.

Eelco Ferwerda, independent consultant in open access and scholarly communication, former director of OAPEN

ACCOMPLISHMENTS: THE TEAM

Even though the team is based across the globe there is a strong sense of belonging amongst the team members. This is mainly based on a strong personal attachment to the shared mission and the shared need to change the system, regardless of the role in the company.

The team sees itself as:

“Grass-root rebels that are truly thinking through the problems of OA publishing and come up with easy-to-use solutions that are not solely stemming only from a business perspective, informed by research and scholarship”.

Team members want to listen to each other regardless of their roles, although with so much happening, it is sometimes difficult to keep everyone in the loop. However, this is something that the team is aware of. There is a willingness to change internal communication workflows to keep everyone informed, especially when the team grows or changes in the future.

STRATEGIC ROADMAP

This strategic roadmap is a result of three interactive sessions in which we worked with the complete team of Thoth. This roadmap represents the vision, ambition and results of Thoth team members.

In the next five years Thoth will sustain and increase its visibility, notably amongst medium sized publishers and continue to connect, develop and adapt secured and tested Tech. This strategic roadmap gives an overview of how Thoth wants to achieve this.

Market

The market for OA book publishing is in its infancy. It might take another 20 years to mature. We don't know yet what the winning business model will be. Creating and sustaining the conditions in which open book publishing can mature is a joint effort by all who believe that publication and distribution of scientific knowledge should be non-commercial, sustainable and inclusive. Thoth will contribute by lowering thresholds and smoothing access.

In the coming five years, Thoth will continue to develop their multisided access:

1. Solidarity with publishers who lack means and skills
2. Robust technology for small and medium sized publishers for OA book publishing
3. Increased bibliodiversity for libraries with a growing catalogue of 3000+ books and 13.000 chapters.

Adaptability is key in a market that changes rapidly. The organisation will therefore seek to remain lean and effective³. Thoth is funded by OA book publishers, for OA book publishing. Thoth will keep servicing its core customers and continuously reach out to new clients and sponsors. Thoth will actively create allyship for OA book publishing, by joining or initiating collectives of like-minded organisations.

To tailor to the needs of small and medium publishers, the Unique Selling Point (USP) of Thoth's services raising the efficiency of the publishing process will be more emphasized in Thoth's communications. Simple reasons to use the services like future savings on time, cost effectiveness and so forth are just as important as its values-based mission. Moreover, the fact that Thoth is seen as a trusted name by other publishers is a central element in its marketing⁴.

"Thoth should try to expand beyond the small sub bubble of small diamond OA publishers they are in. They are not well known amongst medium sized, more traditional university presses".

Eelco Ferwerda, independent consultant in open access and scholarly communication, former director of OAPEN

³ Thoth is aware of the complexities of this ambition, especially when team and market grow

⁴ These insights are based on the input received from stakeholder interviews for this report

Organisation and funding

To pursue its mission, Thoth must be financially healthy. In the last five years the team has grown to 2 FTE positions employed through Thoth, with additional fractional FTEs contributed by freelance team members. Thoth is funded through different income streams, including income generated through the 30+ international library sponsors supporting Thoth via the Open Book Collective, and a substantial amount of project funding received via Open Book Futures. A third, emerging source of funding is the income generated through the establishment of the company’s publisher-facing Thoth Plus dissemination service, the uptake of which is exceeding early expectations. The operational model needed is developed by the core team and led by the three Directors, Vincent van Gerven Oei, Rupert Gatti, and Joe Deville. As mentioned before, the market for OA book publishing is in its infancy. This has made Thoth choose for a broad financing mix.

JUMPING THE FENCES: CUSTOMERS

The **customer base** of Thoth in 2025 consists predominantly of small OA publishers. With the current product range (distribution, hosting, metadata) Thoth will be capable of servicing also medium-sized publishers. This will increase the number of publications and the average customer value.

JUMPING THE FENCES: SPONSORS

The **sponsor base** of Thoth in 2025 consists of 30 institutions. With its current position Thoth can create new collectives and join existing collectives to increase the number of sponsors. Also, Thoth will do research amongst (potential) sponsors to learn more about their motivation⁵.

⁵ Astrid van Wesenbeeck from the Netherlands National Library said that the amount of effort it takes to support is a very important element in the decision to support. Rupert Gatti (Thoth) stated that: 'Thoth does not have a clear insights as to why certain libraries are sponsoring Thoth, nor why some libraries don't.'

JUMPING THE FENCES: FUNDING

The OBF Project grant will provide **funding** for the core team up to end-April 2026. Thoth is aiming to follow up this grant to further develop products. This is in line with the ambition to become a product-orientated company. Thoth foresees opportunities to join in on project calls. Potential partnerships will be set up informal collaborations in case an opportunity presents itself.

Outlook

The market for something to believe in, is infinite, said Gaping Void. Thoth believes in the promise of open. Thoth wants to share this belief and ignite or further stoke the fire for that belief in others. Thoth has a diverse team in age, location, gender, background. They share a passion for open book publishing and a love for pun. Thothally!

The next five years Thoth will share the story of the promise of open, where they can, to whoever they meet. Thoth will be present in this story, hopefully, but others will be as well. Carrying a Thoth bag, with a JUST DOI IT! bumper sticker on their car, or a Rollover RELX Rolodex on their desk.

Thoth will help you rage against the spreadsheet.

"Thoth is in a position to expand. There is so much potential!"

Paula Kennedy, Head of Publishing, University of London Press

